

GoPro Setup for Firefly Recordings

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Abstract

This is a short, practical guide to help you set up your pair of GoPros to record fireflies in 3D. Deploying the GoPros in the field is very quick and simple, but there are a few important details to follow to ensure optimal recording.

1 Setting up the GoPro Max

Not fun, but important. If you are receiving a camera from us, these settings will be already programmed. However, they may need to be re-programmed, for example if you move to a different time zone, or if the battery has been dead for too long, sometimes the settings get erased.

1.1 Turning On/Off

Press once on the Side Button (left of screen) to Power On. Press long (2s) on the Side Button to Power Off. Use Red-Circle Button on top to start recording (see Recording Section).

1.2 General Settings

Swipe screen from top to bottom to enter Setting menu. Enable (blue highlight) only the two top center buttons: music note & jumping bunny (Figure 2). Hit Preferences. Go to General.

- Beep Volume: High (annoying sound, but helpful in the field to know when recording starts/ends).
- QuikCapture : On
- QuikCapture Default: 360
- Default Mode: Last 360 Video
- LEDs: All Off (better to not have a red LED flashing during recording)
- Video Compression: H.264 + HEVC

1.3 Date & Time

In this same menu (Preferences/General)

- Time: set to local time in 24HR format
- Date: set to current date
- Date Format: YY/MM/DD.

1.4 GPS

Under Preferences, scroll down to Regional. GPS: On

1.5 Recording Settings

Exit Preferences by swiping up or pushing side button briefly. You can now swipe left/right to move to the different recording options: time-lapse/video/photo. Go to Video (middle option). In the bottom left corner, make sure you are in 360-mode (spherical symbol). If not, push the symbol to switch between regular and 360. Press bottom center to change recording settings. Push pen symbol on the right. Select "5.6K|30" (30 frame per second). Scroll down under Protune. ISO Min: 6400 (all the way up). Before recording, screen should look like the one in Figure 3.

2 Camera placement

2.1 Finding a good spot

A good spot to place your GoPros should have the following features, ranked by (approximate) order of priority:

1. high firefly activity (as observed on previous nights, if possible)
2. little to no light pollution in the background (if there's a road, street light, etc. anywhere around the cameras, they will show up in the movie)
3. clear and open spot (bushes or trunks close to the cameras will block the view)
4. flat, stable ground (so that they don't tip and fall)

Below are some examples of good spots (minus the fireflies!).

Figure 1: Pairs of GoPros set up at recording sites in AZ, SC, TN. They are side-by-side, on flat and open ground. The spacing is 3ft in the middle picture (yard stick between them), and 6ft otherwise.

2.2 Mounting the tripods

The GoPro tripods are quite sturdy and easy to use. Hold the camera and rotate the handle clockwise to unlock. Pull out to extend. Rotate counter-clockwise to lock in extended position. Unfold the handle to form the tripod. One last thing: it might be good practice to wash the tripods when moving between different locations, to avoid soil cross-contamination.

2.3 Positioning the cameras

Place the cameras side-by-side, with the same side facing the same direction (eg, both screens on the same side). The only important thing to do here is to set or measure the spacing between the cameras. We recommend either 3ft or 6ft, depending on the specifics of the terrain.

3 Recording

3.1 Background (optional)

Whenever possible, it is quite useful to get a picture of the background, which even comes with attached GPS coordinates. If you're able to position your cameras before it gets too dark, here's how to record a nice background frame. For each camera: turn on, swipe left to reach Photo mode. Bottom corner, make sure you are in 360 mode. Just above, set timer to 10s (so you can move away before it captures). The screen should look like Figure 4. Swipe from top to bottom to enter Settings, and then once again to let the date and time appear. Wait for the GPS symbol (center-left) to light up (Figure 5) When it does, it has connected to the satellite, and GPS location will be attached to the image. Push side button briefly, put the camera in place, and push top button. Countdown will begin (you'll hear the beeps), move away. You can power off the camera until ready for movie recording.

3.2 Movie recording

When the time has come, just push the red-circle top recording buttons (ideally within a few seconds from each other). **Make sure you remove the caps!** The cameras don't need to be turned on beforehand. Make sure you hear the start beeps, and they are good to go! The screens will turn off after about a minute. As much as possible, try to move away from the cameras (at least 30ft) and avoid lights within at least 100ft. Full batteries on the GoPro Max will record for about 80min, but you can also turn them off before that. When the battery dies (or they stop recording for any reason), they will make a few quick beeps.

4 Data transfer and wrapping up

4.1 Transfer data

For each camera, a full night of recording (up to 90min) will take about 40GB. Transfer the full content of each SD card on an external drive or upload on a cloud: create 2 separate folders with date and GoPro name (eg, "20220515 C1"), and transfer each SD card in the corresponding folder.

4.2 Empty SD card

Once all data has been transferred, you can erase the SD card to leave space for the next recordings. To do that, turn on your GoPro, go to Preferences/Rest/Format SD card and confirm by pushing "Format".

4.3 Report contextual data

Fill out the form that I will have shared with you about useful contextual data. This includes most notably: date of recording, location of recording, and spacing between the cameras.

5 What happens next?

The movies will then be processed to extract the 3D location of flashes. The resulting product will be a list of (x, y, z, t) coordinates of flash occurrences.

6 Contact

For further questions about this guide and/or camera setup, feel free to contact me at any time: raphael.sarfati@colorado.edu

Figure 2: Enable beeps and QuikCapture. Then hit Preferences to continue setting up your camera.

Figure 3: Screen of video mode before recording. Make sure you remove the lens cap before recording.

Figure 4: Photo mode screen before taking a snapshot of the background.

Figure 5: When GPS has been found (after a few second to a minute), the circled symbol turns bright (as it is on this picture).